

An all-Mach HLLC based scheme for Multi-phase flow with Surface Tension

M.Y. Oomar, A.G. Malan, R.A.D. Horwitz, B.W.S. Jones

Industrial Computational Fluid Dynamics, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Cape Town,
South Africa

G.S. Langdon

Department of Civil and Structural Engineering, University of Sheffield,
United Kingdom

ABSTRACT

This article presents an all-Mach method for two-phase inviscid flow in the presence of surface tension. A modified version of the Hartens, Lax, Leer and Contact (HLLC) approximate Riemann solver based on the work by Garrick et al., (2017) is developed and combined with the popular Volume of Fluid (VoF) method: Compressive Interface Capturing Scheme for Arbitrary Meshes (Ubbink & Issa, 1999) (CICSAM). This novel combination yields a scheme with both HLLC shock capturing as well as accurate liquid-gas interface tracking characteristics. The sonic and two-phase properties of the scheme are assessed using the popular advecting bubble, the Gas-Liquid Riemann problem, and the under-water explosion. The implementation of surface tension in the scheme is verified via the classic static bubble configuration, and the popular Rayleigh-Plesset collapse problem. For the static bubble, the spurious currents are of the order 10^{-8} demonstrating that the scheme is well-balanced. For the Rayleigh-Plesset problem, the maximum relative error on the minimum radius of collapse is found to be within 5% on the coarsest mesh.

KEY WORDS: VoF; Compressible; Surface Tension; CSF; Height Functions.

INTRODUCTION

High-speed multi-phase compressible flow induced by shock waves is of interest to both basic science and engineering. Over the last three decades, different approaches have been proposed to model multi-phase compressible flow (Baer & Nunziato, 1986; Kapila et al., 2001; Shyue, 1998). In this work, we shall employ a homogeneous one-fluid formulation (reduced four-equation) for the inviscid compressible flow modelling of a liquid-gas system in the presence of surface tension effects.

Here, we implement the popular Hartens, Lax, and Leer Contact (HLLC) approximate Riemann solver to capture the sonic characteristics of the flow. However, this solver, on its own, suffers from one major drawback. That is, the smearing of the liquid-gas interface. This has a significant impact on the ability to compute interface curvature accurately and hence surface tension effects were often neglected.

In recent years, to address this smearing, the use of the Volume-of-Fluid (VoF) method in conjunction with Riemann solvers has become popular. Notably, Corot et al., (2020) combined a geometric VoF method with a newly derived Godunov scheme to allow for surface tension effects. However, their method did not employ an HLLC solver. In contrast, Jibben et al., (2019) combined the HLLC solver with a similar geometric VoF method. However, in the latter cited work, conserved variables were reconstructed, and the geometric method was restricted to Cartesian grids.

Hence, in this work, we combine HLLC with the popular algebraic VoF method, the Compressive Interface Capturing Scheme for Arbitrary Meshes (CICSAM) (Ubbink, 1997). The solver is based on the work by Garrick et al., (2017) but however, in contrast to the cited article, we implement a VoF method based on liquid availability. In doing so, we reconstruct primitive variables to allow for a consistent discretisation of the VoF and energy flux. The interface curvature is computed via the celebrated height functions and the convolution method. The implementation is done in the state-of-art code Elemental® (C. J. Visser, A. G. Malan, 2008; Malan & Oxtoby, 2013; Oxtoby & Malan, 2012; Pattinson et al., 2007; Suliman et al., 2014), which was primarily developed for modelling two-phase incompressible or weakly compressible flow.

The paper is organised as follows. First, the governing equations for the homogeneous flow model are detailed. Then, the numerical treatment of these equations is described. Finally, the scheme is validated using a range of benchmark test-cases available in literature for 1-D and 2-D.

NUMERICAL THEORY

Governing Equations

The employed model is based on that by Saurel & Abgrall, (1999) where a homogeneous formulation is derived from their work. The governing equations hence read in compact form

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{U}) = \mathbf{S}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{U} = [\rho, \rho \mathbf{u}, \rho E]^T$. Here, surface tension is included as a